

Performance evaluation of a multi-evaporator NH₃-CO₂ cascade refrigeration system with IHX for seafood processing industry

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ABSTRACT

Seafood processing typically has cooling demands at four different temperatures within the range -40 °C to 0 °C. An NH₃-CO₂ cascade refrigeration system equipped with an internal heat exchanger (IHX) is proposed for the same. The proposed system has two evaporators operating above the cascade condenser with NH₃ as working fluid while two other evaporators are operating below the cascade condenser and have CO₂ as working fluid. IHX in the sub-critical CO₂ refrigeration system produces required sub-cooling at the exit of the condenser, increasing the refrigeration effect, and thus the overall performance improves. The cascade temperature is optimized and the performance of the system is found to be superior to the conventional NH₃ system for various operating conditions. The effects of refrigeration loads, evaporation temperatures, and ambient temperature on the performance of the proposed cascade system are also analyzed.

Keywords: Industrial Refrigeration, NH₃-CO₂ Cascade Refrigeration, Internal Heat Exchanger, Natural Refrigerant, COP, Energy Efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Seafood is an important resource to ensure food security for a large and populous country like India. Harvesting and processing activities also provide large number of employment in coastal areas. At present, the export earnings from seafood contribute about 1% of GDP for India. Seafood processing industries have cooling demand at various temperatures for raw material holding, processing, and long-term storage of products. Crushed ice or flake ice at 0 °C is used for short term storage. Large quantities of chilled water at around 7 °C is utilized for various wash cycles during processing. Blast freezers or plate freezers maintained at -35 °C are used for quick freezing of products to avoid large crystal formation. Refrigerated long term storage facilities are maintained at about -20 °C. In India, most of these refrigeration demands in the on-shore seafood processing plants are met using NH₃ vapor compression refrigeration systems. NH₃ systems have favorable COP for the range of operation, have zero ozone-depleting potential (ODP) and zero global warming potential (GWP). Further, trained workforce for NH₃ system operation and maintenance is readily available. There are, however, local regulations stipulating special safety measures or restricting installation near populated areas because of foul smell, toxicity and flammability of NH₃ in the event of a leakage. There is also a challenge in maintaining the low-temperature evaporator at -35 °C as the evaporating pressure is lower than atmospheric pressure, introducing the possibility of air leakage into the system, which also contains moisture. NH₃ and water form a reactive mixture and can bring about cascading detrimental effects. Further, the volumetric refrigeration capacity, defined as the ratio of refrigeration effect to the volume of refrigerant, decreases substantially for NH₃ from a value of 4797 kJ.m⁻³ at 0 °C, to 1034 kJ.m⁻³ at -35 °C. Therefore, a larger compressor displacement is required for maintaining a lower temperature evaporator reducing its performance. In recent years, CO₂ has re-emerged as a choice of preferred refrigerant owing to its favorable thermophysical properties, especially at the lower temperature range applications. It is a non-toxic, non-flammable fluid having zero ODP and unit GWP. Besides, it has a relatively high refrigerating effect at low temperatures, leading to a more compact system. However, the low critical point and high gas cooler pressure of CO₂ are challenges that reduce its performance in high ambient operations. The challenges can be mitigated to a good extent by adopting a cascade refrigeration system (CRS) in which CO₂ operates at a low temperature circuit (LTC) only.

The NH₃-CO₂ refrigerant pair in CRS is well researched. A few recent publications reported by Mosaffa et al., (2016), Purohit et al., (2018a), Patel et al., (2019) have examined the performance of such a system under the various operating condition and suggested potential modifications in the design for performance enhancement. There is a possibility of improving the performance by incorporating IHX and gas-cooler in NH₃-CO₂ CRS and this is investigated in this study. Although many researchers have analyzed the NH₃-CO₂ refrigerant pair, no study is found in the open literature exploring use of IHX and gas-cooler in a multi-evaporator NH₃-CO₂ CRS. This paper proposes a novel multi-evaporator NH₃-CO₂ CRS and compares its performance with a conventional multi-evaporator NH₃ system for meeting the refrigeration demands in surimi (a variety of processed fish meat) plant.

There are, however, two contradicting effects attributable to the introduction of IHX; on one hand, it increases the specific refrigeration capacity in the evaporator, but on the other hand, it increases the compressor work due to increased specific suction volume of refrigerant. Previous research has shown that the IHX improves overall performance when the working fluid has high heat capacity and within a range of evaporating and condensing temperatures (Domanski et al., 1994). Klein et al., (2000) concluded that installing IHX in the NH₃ refrigeration system reduces the system performance in any operating condition. Zhang et al., (2011) theoretically analyzed the effect of IHX integration with the CO₂ system both in subcritical and trans-critical operations. Llopis et al. (2015) experimentally validated the results obtained by Zhang et al. for the subcritical CO₂ cycle and concluded that refrigeration capacity and COP were reduced by 3.5 % and 3.29 %, respectively, at -25 °C evaporation temperature. However, for a lower temperature of -40 °C in the evaporator, the system COP increased by about 0.45%. Llopis et al. (2016) reported a simulation-based comparative study of an R143-CO₂ CRS with and without IHX and observed an overall increase in COP by 3.7%. Purohit et al. (2018b) experimentally investigated the energetic and exergetic performance of the CO₂ chiller system with IHX for the extreme warm climatic conditions. It is therefore concluded that there is merit in using the IHX with CO₂ subcritical cycle to enhance performance.

2. MODELLING

Cooling demands in a processing plant for a surimi production capacity of 10 tonnes per day was assessed based on a field study carried out at Mumbai city in the western coastal area of India (see Table 1). The various evaporator loads and refrigerant temperatures were assessed assuming 5 °C pinch point in each heat exchanger. The conventional NH₃ refrigeration system used in the surimi plant (see Fig. 1(a)) has a single-stage compressor for medium temperature cooling demand in *ch* and *ice* evaporators, while double stage compressor with intercooling was used for low-temperature evaporators *cs* and *pf*. All the evaporators were flooded type and had separate expansion valves, with refrigerant inlet from a receiver. The corresponding T-s diagram is shown in Fig. 1(b).

Table 1: Cooling demands calculated for various temperature applications

Parameter	Evaporators	Amount	Product Temperature (°C)	Evaporation Temperature (°C)	Refrigeration load (kW)	Load %
Chilled water	<i>ch</i>	100 tonnes/day	7	2	115	38.4
Ice	<i>ice</i>	10 tonnes/day	0	-5	55	18.3
Cold storage	<i>cs</i>	1500 tonnes	-20	-25	70	23.3
Freezing	<i>pf</i>	10 tonnes/day	-35	-40	60	20.0

The proposed NH₃-CO₂ CRS with IHX and its T-s diagram are shown in Figs. 1(c) & 1(d). The system consists of two circuits, a low temperature circuit (LTC) having CO₂ as the refrigerant, and a high temperature circuit (HTC) having NH₃ as a refrigerant. In this arrangement, two evaporators, *ch* and *ice* are in the HTC while another two, *cs* and *pf* are in LTC. These loops are connected with a cascade heat exchanger *cc*, which works as a condenser for LTC while as an evaporator for HTC. Preliminary computation shows that the temperature of refrigerant CO₂ at the exit of *pf* compressor is higher than ambient and dry, therefore, an additional gas-cooler is proposed prior to the cascade condenser. This will reduce the amount of heat supplied to the high-temperature circuit, decreasing the compressor work of the high-temperature circuit.

Figure 1: Baseline NH₃ and proposed CRS system

A mathematical model was developed assuming steady flow steady-state condition across each component, while neglecting pressure drops in pipes and all heat exchangers. Overall mass and energy balance were given with Eq. 1 & 2. Estimated cooling load, the mass flow rate of NH₃, compressor power consumption, and heat loss in the gas cooler are given with Eq. 3-6. Isenthalpic expansion was assumed in all expansion valves. The effectiveness of IHX was considered as 50%. Compressor isentropic efficiencies were assessed from the manufacturer's data and expressed in a polynomial relation in terms of pressure ratio R, as given in Table 2. The system models were coded in EES and simulated for conditions given in Table 3. For the proposed system, the optimum cascade temperature was determined for maximizing COP. Considering the high ambient temperature of Mumbai, the range of condenser temperature simulated is 25 to 45 °C.

Table 3: Compressor isentropic efficiencies

Compresso r	Isentropic efficiency in baseline	Isentropic efficiency in CRS
ch & ice	$\eta_s = -0.0051R^2 + 0.069R + 0.568$	$\eta_s = -0.0051R^2 + 0.069R + 0.568$
cc	-	$\eta_s = -0.005R^2 + 0.0679R + 0.5695$
cs	$\eta_{s,cs} = 0.0596R_{cs}^3 - 0.6135R_{cs}^2 + 2.0485R_{cs} - 1.493$	$\eta_s = 0.00476R^2 - 0.09238R + 0.89810$
pf	$\eta_{s,pf} = 0.0107R_{pf}^3 - 0.1801R_{pf}^2 + 0.981R_{pf} - 1.030$	$\eta_s = 0.00476R^2 - 0.09238R + 0.89810$

$$\sum_{in} \dot{m}_r = \sum_{out} \dot{m}_r \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$\dot{Q} + \sum_{in} \dot{m} h = \sum_{out} \dot{m} h + \dot{W} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$\dot{Q}_{cooling} = \dot{m}_r * \Delta h \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

$$\dot{m}_{cc}(h_{20} - h_{24}) = \dot{m}_{11}(h_{11} - h_{12}) \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

$$\dot{W}_C = (\dot{m}_r * \Delta h_c) / \eta_s \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

$$\dot{Q}_{GC} = \dot{m}_7 * (h_8 - h_9) \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

Effectiveness (ε) of IHX is defined as a ratio of actual heat transfer to the maximum possible heat transfer. It depends on the mass flow rate of the refrigerant at outlets of condenser & evaporators and enthalpy difference between these points and it is expressed in Eq. 7. Fan power consumption is estimated as 3 % of heat rejection. Eq. 8 calculates the COP for the baseline NH₃ system; Eq. 9 calculates the COP for proposed CRS and Eq. 10 calculates the percentage improvement in COP from baseline to the proposed CRS.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{C_c(T_{7a}-T_7)}{C_{min}(T_{12}-T_7)} \text{ or } \varepsilon = \frac{C_h(T_{12a}-T_{12})}{C_{min}(T_{12}-T_7)} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

$$COP_{Baseline} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{ch} + \dot{Q}_{ice} + \dot{Q}_{cs} + \dot{Q}_{pf}}{\dot{W}_{ch} + \dot{W}_{ice} + \dot{W}_{cs} + \dot{W}_{pf} + \dot{W}_{fan}} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

$$COP_{CRS} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{ch} + \dot{Q}_{ice} + \dot{Q}_{cs} + \dot{Q}_{pf}}{\dot{W}_{ch} + \dot{W}_{ice} + \dot{W}_{cs} + \dot{W}_{pf} + \dot{W}_{fan}} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

$$\delta = \frac{(COP_{CRS} - COP_{Baseline})}{COP_{CRS}} * 100 \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

Table 3: Operating condition used in the simulation

Parameters	Values (°C)
Suction superheat in <i>ch</i> and <i>ice</i> line	5
Suction superheat in <i>cc</i> and <i>cs</i> line	10
Suction superheat in <i>pf</i> line	20
Internal superheating in all evaporators	0
Subcooling in LTC and HTC of the system without IHX	0
Approach temperature in <i>cc</i> /gas-cooler/ condenser	5
Condensation temperature (T_{cond})	25-50

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mass flow rate of refrigerants in both the configurations at inlet of respective condensers is compared in Fig. 2(a). The proposed CRS reduces the required NH₃ mass flow rate by 64%. Kærn et al. (2019) have correlated the flow rate with charge reduction in the NH₃ refrigeration system and concluded that a large reduction of refrigerant charge is possible by reducing the flow rate in the circuit. Thus, the reduction of mass flow rate in the CRS has the potential to reduce the refrigerant charge, thereby reducing hazards. It is observed from Fig. 2(b) that power consumption by *ch* & *ice* compressors remains unchanged while there is a reduction in power consumption by *cs* and *pf* compressors leading to an overall 13.1% decrease. This reduction in power consumption is partly due to the reduced condensing pressure of LTC, which is shifted to *cc* compressor in the proposed configuration.

In many seafood processing application, it is preferred that the blast freezers and plate freezers are operated at a temperature below -35 °C, as this speeds up production and also ensure improved product quality due to smaller crystal formation during freezing. The performance of both the systems is next compared for three different low-temperature evaporators -35 °C, -40 °C and -45 °C. As expected, the COP decreases with a decrease in freezer temperature. Using Eq.8 and Eq. 9, variations of COP of both the systems are plotted in Fig.3, as expected the COP decreases with an increase in T_{cond} . However, the CRS shows higher COP for the full range of T_{cond} . At 25 °C condensing temperature, representing winter operation, the COP of baseline system and CRS are 3.23 and 3.88 respectively while at 45 °C condensing temperature, representing summer operation, they are 1.96 and 2.37 respectively.

Figure 2: Refrigerant flow rate (a) and compressor power consumption (b) comparison

Using Eq. 10, the percentage change in COP of baseline and CRS are plotted for three different evaporator temperatures and is presented in Fig.4. It is observed that minimum improvement in the CRS performance in terms of COP is 17 % better than the baseline system. The gain in COP is more pronounced, about 26 %, when the lower evaporator temperature is -45°C and summer time operation. The result establishes the viability of using IHX in spite of its contradicting effects along with a gas-cooler in the CRS system for surimi processing.

Figure 3: COP variation with condenser temperature

Figure 4: Percentage improvement in COP

Figure 5: variation of \dot{Q}_{GC} and \dot{Q}_{HTC}

Fig.5 presents a comparison of the heat rejection rate by the gas-cooler (\dot{Q}_{GC}) to the ambient, computed using Eq. 6, depicted in the primary vertical axis along with the heat transfer rate to the HTC (\dot{Q}_{HTC}) in the secondary vertical axis. \dot{Q}_{GC} increases steadily with an increase in condensing temperature, however, the rate of increase is highest for \dot{Q}_{GC} (-45°C). It is concluded that the increase in the COP in cascade system is a combined effect of the decrease in compressor power consumption due to better thermo-physical properties of CO_2 at lower temperature range, coupled with reduced pressure ratio caused by IHX and reduction of the partial thermal load from heat rejection to the ambient in the gas cooler.

In this work, performance improvement by NH₃-CO₂ CRS equipped with IHX and gas-cooler over the conventional NH₃ system is explored. A possible operational benefit of the proposed CRS is established. However, testing of the proposed system in lab, overall economic analysis based on a fixed and variable cost, the influence of local policy and market incentive or penalty, and long term outlook needs to be examined before implementation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we proposed a novel NH₃-CO₂ cascade refrigeration system having multiple evaporators above and below the cascade temperature and equipped with IHX and a gas-cooler and compared its performance against conventional NH₃ refrigeration for application in a seafood processing plant in warm ambient conditions. It has been observed that the NH₃ charge can be reduced with up-to 64% along with observable improvement in COP with the help of the CRS system. Performance is also evaluated for a lower range of quick freezer operating temperatures at -35 °C, -40 °C, and -45 °C. The proposed CRS system is found more efficient for a wide range of operating conditions.

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